

THE LATEST METHODS USED TO TEACH A FOREIGN LANGUAGE
AT A NON-LINGUISTIC INSTITUTION

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Abstract: The new educational standards, which presume that students have important professional abilities, including foreign language communicative ability, focus research attention on various techniques, technologies, and situations targeted at increasing higher education quality. The article discusses various unique approaches for teaching a foreign language at a non-linguistic university.

Keywords: teaching methods, non-linguistic institutions, teaching features, modern active methods.

Understanding a foreign language in a non-linguistic institution is now regarded an essential component of a specialist's professional training, and having foreign language communicative competence is one of those components. The changing circumstances of the modern world need equivalent adjustments in educational institutions [4-5]. In this sense, the subject of innovation is becoming increasingly relevant for the whole educational system, particularly in the context of foreign language instruction. As many years of experience demonstrate, current techniques of teaching foreign languages provide us with a diverse variety of educational concepts, methods, and technology, both classic and creative. Curriculum developers and instructors prefer one technique over another, depending on the learning objectives.

Furthermore, each teaching approach has benefits and limitations, and their effectiveness is determined by the individual training goals and conditions. In

recent years, the function of a foreign language as a medium of communication has grown dramatically, and this should be considered while teaching a language. The unique aspect of a foreign language is that we teach skills and talents rather than the fundamentals of science, which necessitates extensive speaking practice. Teaching a foreign language is more than just introducing pupils to the language's structure; it is also about teaching them how to utilize the language as a method of communication. As a result, the whole structure of classes and the techniques used must conform with the

As a result, the whole structure of classes and the methods utilized must relate to the actual situation of communication, and training must take place in the context of student engagement. A teacher's work system for ensuring the results of teaching a foreign language must include the implementation of the following technologies: communicative learning technology, technology for understanding the communicative meaning of a text, game technologies, collaborative learning technologies, project technologies, and so on. The term "technology" is drawn from the realm of manufacturing. At our perspective, pedagogical technologies for teaching a foreign language at a non-linguistic institution should be defined as a collection of forms, methods, teaching approaches, and educational instruments that are employed systematically in the educational process.

Educational innovations strive to shape the personality, its capacity to engage in scientific, technological, and inventive activities, and to update the educational process's content. In terms of the educational process, innovation entails incorporating something new into the aims, content, techniques, and forms of teaching and rearing, as well as organizing collaborative activities between the instructor and the student. Innovation in education refers to the ability to incorporate sophisticated scientific advancements into the educational process in order to create professionals who can independently carry out additional innovations during their scientific and practical careers. The necessity to address

the educational crisis has led to the development of novel technology for teaching foreign languages.

The technology of education of the last century, based on scientific logic, should be transformed into a technology based on the principles of "knowledge to skill", based on the laws of cognitive activity of students, which should be aimed at achieving the heights of mastery. Creative, spiritual and moral activity. with graduates. In the new paradigm of education, the student is an active subject of cognitive activity, who organizes the educational process with the help of new forms, participates in a dialogue with the teacher.. Today, a student is an active, creative person who not only possesses certain knowledge, but also studies, searches for and receives the necessary information, for which he uses various sources, including mass media, and is able to constantly develop [20].. The most important trends in the development of modern society related to the processes of globalization and information are directly reflected in the educational process and especially in the field of foreign language education.. According to research and work experience, the situation of teaching foreign languages in technical universities can be described as a struggle between traditional education and creativity. Of course, the dominance of one type of doctrine leads to extremes.

If norms take priority over the new, research and practice will stagnate, and if we ignore traditions in the quest of innovations, science will have nothing to rely on. As a result, an appropriate mix of traditions and innovations is required to propel pedagogical science forward and grow on the basis of experience. We need technologies that are successful, contribute to the advancement of pedagogical science, and prepare students for future professional activities.

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